

Butonese Muslims

also known as "Orang Butung or Orang Butuni"

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Sufism

The Butonese, also known as Orang Butung or Orang Butuni is a collective term that embraces diverse ethnic groups (such as the Tukang Besi, Muna* and Wolio) from the island of Buton and neighboring islands that constitute the Indonesian province of Sulawesi Tenggara (Southeast Sulawesi). The Butonese population (estimated at ~ 236,000) mostly professes Islam. Historically seafarers, the Butonese migrated from Johor (today's Malaysia) to the island of Buton and have subsequently immigrated to the Moluccas, the center of Indonesia's spice production in search of better economic opportunities. The Butonese Sultanate (founded ~ 1540), with the conversion of the Sixth Raja of Buton to Islam, occupied a strategic position in the coastal trade between Java and Makassar, on one hand and the Moluccas, on the other. The sovereignty of the Butonese Sultanate was challenged around the seventeenth century due to the power struggle between Makassar and Ternate for the control of the spice trade. By 1613, Butonese Sultan La Elangi liaised with the Dutch East India Company (VOC) to free the Sultanate from the power struggle between Makassar and Ternate. But by 1669, the Sultanate was placed under the suzerainty of Pax Neerlandica by principle although in practice, the principality was independent until 1906. Subsequent to Indonesian independence (1945) and the transfer of power to the Indonesian Republic (1949), Buton continued to remain a Sultanate until 1960 when the principality was merged into the Indonesian republic. * Muna do not consider themselves Butonese although the Muna-Buton languages belong to the Celebic sub-group of Austronesian family to which Wolio belongs. So, it would be safe to generalize that Butonese refers to the inhabitants of the former Sultanate of Buton (prior to 1960).

Date Range: 1500 CE - 2002 CE

Region: Southeast Sulawesi

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Indonesia, Southeast Sulawesi

Buton or Boeton is an island of Indonesia located off the Southeastern peninsula of the Indonesian province of Sulawesi Tenggara (Southeast Sulawesi). Geographical coordinates: Latitude: -5° 02' 60.00" S Longitude: 122° 52' 59.99" E

I want Indonesia's Sulawesi Tenggara province (Southeastern Sulawesi) with these islands: Islands: Wowoni, Buton, Muna and Kabena. I want this map from the website: <https://latitude.to/articles-by-country/id/indonesia/36428/buton> Thank you.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: J.W. Schooli, " Butonese," in: Encyclopedia of World Cultures: South and Southeast Asia, Vol. 5, edited by Paul Hockings (New York: Prentice Hall International, 1993).

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://openresearch-repository.anu.edu.au/handle/1885/150325>
- Source 1 Description: Vermeij Jennifer, " The Formation of the Butonese Sultanate : Dutch Political Involvement in the Creation and Maintenance of the Butonese Sultanate" (ANU MA Thesis, 2000).

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: Hubungan Butin dengan Negeri lain, British Library, EAP212/1/1, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP212-1-1>
- Source 2 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP212-1-6#?c=0&m=0&s=0&cv=0&xywh=-2525%2C-261%2C8549%2C5213>
- Source 2 Description: Makhfani I, British Library, EAP212/1/6, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP212-1-6>
- Source 3 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP212-2-3#?c=0&m=0&s=0&cv=0&xywh=-459%2C-159%2C5189%2C3164>
- Source 3 Description: Kitab Hidayat Al Basyir fi Mar'rifat Al-Qadir, British Library, EAP212/2/3, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP212-2-3>

Notes: All the three manuscripts are in Arabic script and belong to the 19th/ early 20th century. The first manuscript Hubungan Butin dengan Negeri Lain in Malay but in Arabic script highlights the maritime contacts of the Butonese. The second manuscript Mafkani I, highlights the criteria for selecting one's spouse (in Arabic script). The third manuscript Kitab Hidayat Al Basyir fi Mar'rifat Al-Qadir, in Arabic, highlights the attributes of Allah and His Messenger, the tenets of Islam and meaning and declaration of faith (kalimat syahadat).

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– I don't know

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The Butonese immigrants in Maluku, mostly petty traders and plantation workers were targeted during the Maluku sectarian conflict (1999-2002). See for instance, "Indonesia: The Violence in Ambon," Human Rights Watch, March 17, 1999. URL: <https://www.hrw.org/legacy/reports/1999/ambon/amron.htm#TopOfPage>.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– I don't know

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 225000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 80

Notes: 80% Islam; 20% Christian, mostly Protestant Christianity in the southern half of the island of Muna and a smaller number of Catholics.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: Butonese are predominately Sunni Muslim with smaller community of Christians in the southern part of the island of Muna. The Muna people refuse to be identified as Butonese.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– I don't know

– Yes

Notes: Sarana Agama or Sarana Hukumu in the former Butonese Sultanate (prior to 1960) was the religious council in charge of matters related to Islam.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: King Murhum's tombstone in Bau Bau regency (kabupaten).

↳ Cemeteries:

– I don't know

↳ Temples:

– No

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– I don't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Istana Malige, a four-storeyed wooden structure topped with a pineapple carving, representing the Butonese sultanate.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Maalige Palace

– Yes [specify]: Palace Mosque inside Wolio Fort (two-tiered hipped roof)

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: A pineapple carving tops the Istana Malige, representing the Buton Sultanate. Palace mosque inside Wolio Fort is built by rectangular plan, with two-tiered hipped roof, a slightly irregular style (see for e.g. Sakai 2016).

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for all

Notes: Every able-bodied Muslim must undertake the Hajj pilgrimage at least once in their lifetime.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Hari Kiamat or the Day of Judgment as specified in Islam.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: There is a strong Butonese belief in reincarnation. Many Butonese can tell which deceased child or grandfather has returned (Schoorl 1993).

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– I don't know

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– I don't know

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: ~2001, most Butonese followed the five pillars of Islam such as the confession of the faith, praying five times a day, fasting during Ramadan, giving alms to the poor and undertaking the Haj pilgrimage to Mecca, if able. But until the 1950s, harvest festivals such as bongka ta'o (opening of the year) and protection rights such as kaagono liwu or village cleansing rituals would be performed to appease the territorial spirits. Many of these rituals are not held openly as they contradict Islamic tenets (Palmer 2013).

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Both human and non-human
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Supernatural beings (particularly arwah or spirits of deceased can bestow rewards or punishments on individuals according to their behavior).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– Yes
Notes: Spirits of deceased relatives known as Arwah (Schoorl 1993).

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Yes
Notes: Various guardian spirits of houses, praus, villages, harvest beings, possession spirits that cause illness, and helpful spirits that provide guidance (Schoorl 1993).

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– Yes [specify]: Butonese Islam, influenced by Sufism, incorporates Hindu beliefs of reincarnation.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Yes [specify]: Behavior

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: Islamic Eschatology.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: The co-existence of Adat or customary law with Sharia (a religious law forming part of Islamic tradition).

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– I don't know

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– I don't know

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– I don't know

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society
– All individuals within contemporary world
– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):
– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):
– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:
– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is mandatory during the Holy Month of Ramadan (Bulan Puasa).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Muslims are required to pray five times a day.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– I don't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: The consumption of pork is forbidden (haram) in Islam.

↳ Hair:

– I don't know

↳ Dress:

– I don't know

↳ Ornaments:

– I don't know

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– I don't know

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Butonese is the historical term used to denote ethnic groups such as the Wolio who inhabited the erstwhile Butonese Sultanate until 1960.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: According to Indonesia's decentralized set-up since 2002, disaster relief is available through the provincial and kabupaten administrations, supported by central grants.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Notes: The Adat of the Butonese stipulates reverence for elders.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Social stratification is an extant feature of Butonese society. Among the Wolio people in particular, the Kaomu and the Walaka constitute the ruling class and the aristocracy, respectively. In Wolio mythology, the king descended from the sky. Therefore the Kaomu reside on the hills. The class-based social stratification of Wolio is described in the mid-nineteenth century Wolio poem *Anjonga Inda Malusa*, that illustrated the importance of the Papara or villager (refer Umar, Fasli, Rosyidah 2018). In *Anjonga Inda*, the papara are metaphorically described as the feet of the human body whereas the Kaomu and Walaka are described as the human body itself. The class-based social stratification in Butonese society is linked to division of human labor, akin to the varna system of ancient India.

– Yes

Notes: La Ode and Wa Ode are status markers for Butonese men and women respectively (Song 2018). Apart from social stratification, Butonese society can be divided into different ethnicities such as Wolio (the Kaomu and Wolaka belong to Wolio), *Tukang Besi*, *Cia-Cia*, *Katobengke* and *Laporo* who were traditionally classified as "Non-Wolio."

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the local administration, in Indonesia's decentralized administration.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the village and district administration, in Indonesia's decentralized setup.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the Indonesian and provincial government (Sulawesi Tenggara).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– I don't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– I don't know

Notes: Customary Adat.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– I don't know

Notes: The Wolio language is written in Arabic script. But its usage is declining in Buton because both Butonese languages and Arabic script are increasingly being replaced by bahasa Indonesia and the Latin alphabet.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Bahasa Indonesia.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Bahasa Indonesia.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– I don't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: In Indonesia's decentralized set-up the Indonesian government disburses food aid to the provincial and local governments.

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